

ASSESSING THE TEACHERS' COMPETENCIES IN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION ON INSTRUCTIONAL METHODOLOGIES IN THE NEW NORMAL

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ABSTRACT

The study explores the novice teachers' competencies in integrating education technology in lesson preparation. The paper is anchored in the professional standards for teachers, specifically, domains that focus on the positive use of ICT. The study utilized an explanatory research design. The selected one hundred thirty-two novice teachers answered the online survey questionnaire introduced using Google forms and ten (10) participants for an online interview through purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using Blended Teaching Readiness survey questionnaire and semi-structured questionnaire, respectively. Analysis of data progressed through SPSS statistical software and thematic coding. The study reveals that the self-evaluation of novice teachers on their abilities is very competent. Qualitative data exposed the different struggles in teacher preparations in instructional methodologies. Hence, novice teachers must undergo additional professional development to enhance their competencies in designing online learning. Teacher education institutions must intensify in equipping teachers with knowledge on integrating technology in lesson preparations. The government must provide resources for the teachers that will help them prepare instructional materials such as ICT rooms, technicians for technical support, laptops, and internet connectivity. Enough time will also help teachers to design better instructional materials for their class. The current situation of the education system of our country needs a more significant push and optimistic view that we will be able to make progressive change. Teachers should think of personal initiative, welcome the possible ways to enhance the current system, and become part of reforms to help our country uplift and face challenges and endeavors.

Keywords: Educational Technology, Instructional methodologies, professional development; and Teachers' professional standards.